

Oxidation of $\alpha \cdot \beta$ Unsaturated Acid. Part II. V(v) Oxidation of Cinnamic Acid*

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The V(v) oxidation of Cinnamic acid has been found to obey a second order rate law. Complexation and concurrent reaction is indicated whereas Michaelis-Menton type of kinetics is not observed. The values of rate constant did not correlate with dielectric constant of the medium. The product was found to be 1 : 4 diphenyl, 1 : 5 butadiene from its i.r. and n.m.r. spectra.

MANY dicarboxylic acids like oxalic¹, malonic² etc. and hydroxy acids like mandelic³, atrolactic⁴ etc. have been subjected to V(v) oxidation. Aliphatic acids resist attack by V(v) though branched chain and unsaturated acids are some what attacked⁵. Aromatic acids have not been subjected to this type of oxidation and therefore cinnamic acid oxidation has been taken up.

Sodium vanadate, used for V(v), was of analar B.D.H. variety. The rate of oxidation was followed by estimating unused V(v) at different intervals of time by the procedure reported earlier⁴.

The oxidation has been done in sulphuric acid-acetic acid mixture. The concentration of cinnamic acid has been too much in excess so that the rate of reaction obeys first order rate law. The first order rate constant (k_1) is found to decrease with increasing NaVO_3 (Table 1). Considering this to be due to ionic strength effect, the rate has been followed with

changing Na_2SO_4 with no success (Table 2). This type of behaviour is also observed with cases of possible complexation and concurrent reaction. A

TABLE 2. VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT AT VARYING $[\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4]$ FOR THE V(v) OXIDATION OF CINNAMIC ACID.

$10^3 [\text{V(v)}] = 8.62M$, $10^3 [\text{CA}] = 150.0$ $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.40M$.
HAC : $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 66.8 : 33.2$ (v/v), Temp. = 35°

$10^3 [\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4]$	140.0	120.0	100.0	60.0	40.0
$10^6 k$ in sec^{-1}	15.1	14.5	15.0	14.6	14.5

TABLE 3. VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT AT VARYING % OF HAC.

$10^3 [\text{CA}] = 150.0M$; $10^3 [\text{V(v)}] = 8.62M$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.40M$.
Temp. 35°

%HAC (V/v)	80.8	76.8	74.8	70.8	70.0	68.0	66.8
$10^3/D$	45.6	42.4	41.0	38.0	37.5	36.0	34.9
$10^6 k$ in sec^{-1}	69.2	67.5	67.0	54.0	33.5	26.9	16.6

TABLE 1. V(v) OXIDATION OF CINNAMIC ACID AT VARYING $[\text{V(v)}]$ AND AT VARYING $[\text{CA}]$. $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 3.04M\%$; HAC = 71.28 (8v/v), Temp. = 35°

10^3CA	10^3V(v)	$10^6 k_1$	$\frac{10^6 k_1}{10^3 \text{CA}}$
150.0	17.20	44.00	—
150.0	14.34	50.50	—
150.0	11.50	63.00	4.02
150.0	8.62	100.18	—
125.0	11.50	52.48	4.20
100.0	37.50	37.40	3.74
075.0	11.50	26.20	3.40
050.0	11.50	20.94	4.18

TABLE 4. VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT AT VARYING V(v) IN PERCHLORIC ACID MEDIUM.

$10^3 [\text{CA}] = 150.0M$; $[\text{HClO}_4] = 0.14M$; $[\text{NaClO}_4] = 0.091M$.
HAC : $\text{H}_2\text{O} = 66.8 : 33.2$ (v/v). Temp. = 35°

10^3V(v)	16.50	13.60	10.85
$10^6 k$ in sec^{-1}	4.11	4.44	3.84

linear plot of $\log k$ vs. $1/[\text{V(v)}]$ (Fig. 1) with a slope of $+0.62$ corroborates this view point. In HClO_4 medium, however, the values of k_1 do not change with changing $[\text{NaVO}_3]$. The oxidation rate (k_1) changes with changing $[\text{CA}]$ such that, the bimolecular rate constant ($k_2 = k_1/[\text{CA}]$) remains a constant.

*Extracted from the M.Sc thesis.

To examine the possibility of complexation and simultaneous decomposition a plot of k^{-1} vs. CA^{-1} has been prepared with no intercept (Fig. 1).

The rate of the reaction has also been followed in different acetic acid contents in the reaction mixture. Therefore a plot of (Fig. 2) $\log k$ vs. $1/D$ has been

prepared and a curvature with a plateau beyond 75% HAC is noted. The steep increase in rate may be ascribed to the formation of an acetyl derivative by replacement of hydroxyl hydrogen by an acetyl group, thus making the central vanadium ion a better electrophile. At higher acetic acid this process

might have been complete and the values of k_1 , hence, remain constant. No indication of free radical mechanism is exhibited since polymerisation of acrylonitrile did not take place. But the nature of the product indicates a free radical pathway. The polymerisation of acrylonitrile has not been observed perhaps owing to the formation of a very reactive free radical (not a resonance stabilised system), which immediately dimerises to give a product. The attempt to determine the stoichiometry (i.e., at lower concentration of $[CA]$ and higher $[V(v)]$) failed since no perceptible reaction was noted even after a month. In analogy to the $Ce(IV)$ oxidation of cinnamic acid⁶ and from the similar nature of the product with both the oxidants it was assumed that two moles of $V(v)$ are absorbed/mole of CA . The reaction mechanism has been formulated in the following scheme. (Scheme-I).

Scheme I

The product was isolated under reaction conditions (i.e., excess of cinnamic acid and less of $Ce(IV)$). A mixture containing a $NaHCO_3$ soluble component (a) and a $NaHCO_3$ insoluble component (b) has been isolated. The component (a) has been characterised to be cinnamic acid itself from all tests. The component (b) was white in colour. On nmr analysis a multiplet centred at 2.6τ (monosubstituted benzene), two doublets at 2.25τ and 3.6τ ($J = 16$ cps, 2Ha re) are obtained. The area under the peaks correspond to 2:10:2. Therefore the compound is characterised to be 1:4 diphenyl 1:3 butadiene. (Found: C, 92.9%, H, 13.3%, Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{14}$: C, 93.2%, H, 13.6%, m.p. 68° , Lit. 70°).

TABLE 5. VALUES OF RATE CONSTANT AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES, ENERGY OF ACTIVATION AND ENTROPY OF ACTIVATION VALUES FOR THE $V(v)$ OXIDATION OF CINNAMIC AND *p*-METHOXY CINNAMIC ACID.

$10^3[V(v)] = 8.16M$, $10^3[CA] = 150.0M$, $10^5(p\text{-OMe CA}) = 75.0$
 $[H_2SO_4] = 2.4M$, $HAC:H_2O = 64.0:36.0$ $V(v)$.

Name of the compound	$10^3 k_2$ in $M^{-1}sec^{-1}$				E in K.cals mole ⁻¹	OS ⁺ in e.u.
	30°	35°	40°	45°		
CA	0.035	0.058	0.08	0.101	11.98	-39.6
<i>p</i> -MeO CA	-	35.2	43.8	57.3	9.44	-30.5

The species, I, is a resonance stabilised system with a benzylic carbonium ion. So the rate determining step involves, not only the formation of a free radical but also the formation of a benzylic carbonium ion.

Therefore *p*-methoxy cinnamic acid was also subjected to this oxidation and the rate constant (k_2) found to be 6,000 times high. Assuming the intermediate to be a C^+ and the values of σ^+ would hold good, the values of ρ^+ has been calculated to be—4.87, which is in agreement with most of the reactions proceeding with a carbonium ion intermediate. Bromination of styrene⁷, hydration of styrene⁸, which are known to proceed through a carbonium ion intermediate have ρ^+ value —4.3 and —3.2 respectively. The values of energy of activation and entropy of activation (Table 5) have been derived. The negative entropy of activation values may be due to solvation around transition state due to dispersal of charge.

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References

1. J. R. JONES and W. A. WATERS. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4757.
2. H. KURIHARA and T. NAJAKI, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1962, **83**, 708.
3. T. J. KEMP and W. A. WATERS. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1489, 3101, 3193.
4. J. N. KAR, G. B. BEHERA and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 400.
5. J. R. JONES, W. A. WATERS and J. S. LITTLER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 630.
6. G. B. BEHERA, R. C. ACHARYA, K. K. MUKHERJEE and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (communicated).
7. J. H. ROLSTON and K. YATES. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 1483.
8. Y. OKAMOTO, T. INUKAI and H. C. BROWN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 4972.